

STATE REGULATION OF INSURANCE ACTIVITY IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Sanzhar Rajabovich Sherov

PhD, Senior Lecturer of Tashkent Financial Institute (Republic of
Uzbekistan)

Shoydaliev Umid Eshkuvat ugli

Lecturer of Termez State University (Republic of Uzbekistan)

Abstract: The article considers the conceptual foundations of the regulators of the institution in the conditions of innovative development of the economy. It notes that the institution as a process of defining and securing norms, rules, statuses, roles is regulated and modeled. On the basis of system analysis, a classification is given which, in the author's opinion, is applicable to research and analysis of the internal structure of the system mechanism with the aim to identify effective forms and instruments of state regulation of insurance activities.

Keywords. institution, institution theory, insurance institution, institutional regulation tools, direct regulation, indirect regulation, state regulation, methods of state regulation, forms of state regulation, system of state regulation, prudential regulation. institutional regulation tools.

Introduction.

The conceptual basis of the theory of institution goes back to the idea of equilibrium. As a process of defining and fixing norms, rules, statuses, roles and bringing them into the system, based on this, the institution is regulated and modeled.

The study of institutional regulators in an innovative economy is becoming particularly relevant. In theoretical sources, the process of institutionalization is considered as a set of a huge number of institutions. The question of the relationship between the state and other institutions is solved according to the formula "first among equals" and it is noted that the time has come "to consider the state not as

sovereignty, but as an institution of institutions" [1].

Reforming the public administration system through its decentralization, gradual reduction of state regulation and administrative impact on economic sectors, in order to expand market management mechanisms aimed at developing a competitive environment, the introduction of modern public-private partnership mechanisms aimed at improving the effectiveness of mutually beneficial cooperation in the implementation of the country's development objectives[2].

Analysis and review of the situation.

State regulation in the conditions of innovative economic development needs new forms and tools [3]. The existing trends require a deep study of the problem of the effectiveness of economic regulators. For example, modern problems inherent in developed foreign economic systems (EU countries, USA, etc.) indicate a modification of the practice of state regulation in favor of market regulators. Currently, there is a process of gradual strengthening and complication of state regulation of financial and economic processes.

However, it must be remembered that the theory of state regulation finds its expression in the practice of macroeconomic policy of the state. Since real economic systems function in different economic conditions, the basic prerequisites for the development of these systems differ significantly.

In modern conditions of integration of various branches of financial institutions of the economy (banking, investment and insurance), convergence of products, i.e. modern trends in the development of the innovation market of these industries have necessitated the creation of systems of intersectoral financial regulation[4]. The study of the system of state regulation is mainly carried out at the macroeconomic level. But it should be noted that the level of macroeconomic analysis does not allow us to fully take into account the peculiarities of the

institution, the industry specifics of the regulatory system. This is quite true for any branch of the economy, and, accordingly, is typical for insurance activities.

The main part.

Modern achievements in the field of macroeconomic theory do not take into account the proportions and dynamics of the development of a particular branch of the economy, which should determine the direction and content of state regulation, in particular, the relationship between the theory and practice of macroeconomic regulation, the decline in the role of state regulators is debatable (Fig.1).

Fig.1. The nature of theoretical approaches to issues of state regulation[5].

Therefore, research is needed at the mesoeconomical level (as industries develop, other indicators will be added for evaluation): in relation to a certain industry, an intersectoral complex, in a specialized market, at the level of a separate economic institute. It cannot be said that the issues of insurance regulation have not been studied at all. Various aspects of state regulation of insurance are considered in several studies. They are mainly devoted to the issues of monitoring the solvency of insurance organizations and were practically not linked to the fundamental theory of state regulation of the economy[6].

A number of publications are devoted to such problems of regulation of insurance activities as the development and organization of compulsory insurance, the introduction of new mandatory types of insurance, the role and place of state bodies in solving these tasks[7]. The result of these studies is the definition of the tasks of state regulation of insurance in one direction or another, however, the institutional aspect of regulation of insurance activity is practically not considered. At the same time, the object of research is one of the segments of the financial sector of the economy of Uzbekistan, which has perhaps the most developed and dynamic institutional base.

The liberalization of the economy and adequate institutional transformations of insurance during the transition to a market economy have led to the fact that relations in the insurance market have become largely spontaneous, unregulated. This has become one of the main reasons for the bankruptcy of newly formed insurance companies. This situation was caused by the lack of necessary regulatory norms that would put the activities of capital in the appropriate legislative framework and prevent the penetration of non-professional agents into the market. The institutional foundations of insurance did not correspond to the objective economic needs of society. The Insurance Institute did not perform many of its inherent

functions, such as ordering and structuring relationships, reducing the risk of uncertainty, and ensuring security. The situation began to change quite quickly as a result of the adoption of relevant regulatory legal acts: the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Insurance Activity" and others[8].

Insurance is an independent institutional form, as well as a subsystem of the economic system of society as a whole. Therefore, it can quite reasonably act as an independent object of analysis of problems of state regulation. This will allow, with a certain amount of abstraction and assumptions, to approximate and model the process of regulation at the macro level, determine its necessity, basic methods and forms.

Traditionally, the need for state regulation of insurance activities is derived from the social significance of insurance, which consists in citizens receiving compensation for material and financial losses, additional income.

The state determines the priority directions of the industry's development, targets and mechanisms for achieving them, develops an appropriate regulatory framework and thus forms state policy. At the same time, one of the main tasks of the state is defined as "ensuring the reliability of the activities of insurers"[9]. However, with this approach, in our opinion, the objective perception of insurance as an open, complex, multi-subject system is artificially narrowed and thereby simplified. In this regard, there is a need for an in-depth analysis that allows us to give a more complete justification, to consider the content and reasons for state regulation of insurance activities, to identify the most effective regulatory tools.

The reasons for state regulation of insurance activity are formulated, first of all, based on its institutional nature. The need for state regulation of insurance activities is caused by the following reasons:

- lack of competition and inability to achieve complete equilibrium in the

market;

- incompleteness of information and the influence of factors;
- the presence of high transaction costs;
- specificity and social significance of the insurance product.

In practical terms, perfect competition is impossible in the real insurance market. The formation of demand and supply of insurance services occurs differently than in conventional commodity markets. Due to the specificity of the product being sold, the insurer contributes to the formation of demand. In addition, the asymmetry of information is particularly pronounced in the insurance market. The probabilistic and random nature of the insurance product makes the insurer more aware of the potential client. Lack of information can block interaction and contribute to the absence of a contract. In the insurance business, the need to obtain information for more accurate statistical calculations is particularly acute. This, in turn, causes an increase in transaction costs, which can be minimized thanks to state control.

As you know, the market does not always provide balance, and therefore the regulation of the interests of its participants is achieved through state regulation and the social orientation of this industry also assumes the presence of such regulatory instruments. "With shortcomings or lack of state regulation, it is easy to put your interest ahead of the interests of policyholders"[10]. Socially significant types of insurance are of a public nature, therefore they are subject to state regulation.

State regulation is one of the main conditions for ensuring the economic security of society. In addition to the risks inherent in the national economy, modern innovation processes significantly increase the risks of financial security. Therefore, the State is called upon to create conditions for ensuring economic security and compliance with the rule of law.

In addition, one of the tasks of state regulation is the elimination, reduction of negative externalities that occur in almost any branch of the economy, and in insurance activities. In our opinion, an example of externality within the industry in the future may be the activities of foreign insurance companies that are able to offer a more attractive product, as a result of which the competitiveness of insurance products of domestic insurance organizations will decrease. In this case, it should be noted that the emergence of strong competitors will always stimulate the development of the insurance institute. "Foreign intervention" in insurance contributes to strengthening the positions of economic agents. This will be the positive externalities. Outside of insurance activity, the aggressive pricing policy of insurance companies can be called a negative external effect, which leads to an increase in the costs of economic entities and, accordingly, to an increase in prices. Prevention, elimination of negative effects from the functioning of insurance organizations is actually the main purpose and reason for state regulation.

The sectoral features of state regulation of insurance activities are fully manifested at the level of its methods, forms and tools. The lack of clarity in understanding, defining and distinguishing the main methods and forms of state regulation cannot but affect the process of developing, forming and implementing a regulatory mechanism in practice. Most of the research in this area is of a general economic, i.e. industry-wide nature, while the most relevant is government regulation in specific industries.

Any industry has special characteristics that significantly influence the definition of the goal-setting of state regulation, the application of its forms and tools. The specifics of insurance activity in the conditions of Uzbekistan, of course, are reflected in the content and forms of state regulation. Traditionally, direct and indirect regulation are distinguished. The structure of the institution of state

regulation is described by a set of its methods, forms and tools.

There is still no consensus regarding the classification of forms and methods of state regulation of the insurance institute. In order to systematize the definition of methods and forms of regulation, the generally accepted essence of these terms can be taken as a basis. Method as "a way to achieve a goal, solve a specific task"[11]. The form is "the external expression of any content"[12]. The method is a system of any functional actions, the form is a means of influencing the application of a particular method.

State regulation of insurance activities is carried out by certain methods, which are based on the use of appropriate forms. Traditionally, direct and indirect regulation are distinguished (Fig.2).

Fig.2. Forms and methods of state regulation of insurance activity[13].

In this process, it is more correct to separate the methods at the level of state regulation instruments. In this regard, the following arguments about the need to separate methods into direct and indirect (depending on the method of influence) are confirmed:

- **direct regulation**, where direct state influence is carried out through the

"establishment" of an institute, the introduction of a norm, a rule. An example is the introduction of compulsory insurance (the essence of this phenomenon is expressed by the economic nature of the relations that develop within the framework of compulsory insurance by virtue of the law, i.e. the method of its implementation is exclusively legal, since compulsory insurance is always based on the adoption of an appropriate regulatory act by the state);

- **indirect regulation**, based on methods that are aimed at the external environment in which the economic entity operates. This creates conditions in the external environment, according to which the activity of this subject is adjusted. And these methods, as well as methods of direct influence, can be based on regulatory legal acts, rules.

In our opinion, when separating the methods of state regulation into direct and indirect, it makes no sense to carry out detailed detailing, which may lead away from the intended goal, i.e. classification of methods. The separation of methods of state influence in the future will allow to systematize the forms of regulation by the state. At the same time, the separation of methods of regulation is proposed to be carried out through their "binding" in accordance with specific areas subject to regulation or with the scope of regulated relations, in this particular case with an insurance institution.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Thus, taking into account the identifying features, the methods of state influence on the insurance institution can be reduced to economic administration, financial regulation, strategic and tactical forecasting, monetary regulation.

Forms of institutional regulation (administration) consists in determining the external conditions for the functioning of economic entities, the "rules of the game" in the market, the establishment of legal norms in specialized markets.

State regulation is one of the main conditions for ensuring the economic security of society. In addition to the risks inherent in the national economy, modern innovation processes significantly increase the risks of financial security.

Economic regulation is a functional active, direct participation of the state through its authorized bodies. This form of state regulation based on strategic and tactical forecasting makes it possible to determine the directions of development of the economic system as a whole, in particular, a specific branch of the economy.

REFERENCES

1. Fundamentals of public law [Text]:monograph.//Oriu Maurice. [comp. :Kurakin R.S. et al.] - Moscow: INFRA-M, 2013. -572.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. UP-4947 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" .//<http://lex.uz>
3. Kamyshova A.B., Pogorelskaya L.N. The combination of planned and market principles in the state regulation of the modern economy.//Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Natural Sciences.2013. No. 1. pp. 14-17.
4. Insurance and risk management: problems and prospects: monograph.//A.P. Arkhipov, A.N.Bazanov, S.A.Belozerov [et al.];Edited by S.A.Belozerov, N.P.Kuznetsova.- M.: Prospect, 2017. -528 p.
5. Instruction "On the procedure for conducting inspections of the activities of insurance organizations by the State Insurance Supervision Inspectorate" [Registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 741 dated June 7, 1999].//<http://lex.uz>
6. Based on the analysis of the nature of theoretical approaches compiled by the author.
7. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 286 dated July 8, 1998 "On measures for state regulation of insurance activities". //<http://lex.uz>.
8. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Insurance activity" No. 358-11 of April 5, 2002.//<http://lex.uz> ; Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 31.01.2002 N UP-3022 "On measures for further liberalization and development of the insurance market".//<http://lex.uz>; Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated

27.11.2002 N413 "On measures for further development of the insurance services market" .//<http://lex.uz>

9. Regulations on the solvency of insurers and Reinsurers (Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2008, No. 20-21, Article 178; 2010, No. 52, Article 526; 2014, No. 46, Article 554; 2015, No. 52, Article 650; 2017, No. 29, Article 714).//<http://lex.uz>
10. Avdasheva, S., Shastitko, A. Modernization of antimonopoly policy in Russia. // With Avdasheva, A.Shastitko //Economic issues.- 2005. - No. 5. - pp.101-106.
11. Adamchuk, N. G. The world insurance market on the way to globalization.//N. G. Adamchuk/ - Moscow : Moscow State Institute of International Relations (University); Russian Political Encyclopedia (ROSPEN), 2004. - 590 p.
12. Andrianov, V. D. Evolution of the basic concepts of economic regulation from the theory of mercantilism to the theory of self-regulation.//V. D. Andrianov. - M.: Ekonomika, 2008. - 326 p.
13. The figure is compiled by the author based on the analysis. forms and methods of state regulation of insurance activity.